

Correction

Correction: Gaspari et al. A Simplified Algorithm to Predict Indoor Microclimate in Case of Courtyard Covering. A Case Study for the Courtyard of Palazzo Poggi in Bologna. *Eng* 2020, 1, 222–239

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The authors wish to make the following corrections to this paper [1]:

There was a mistake in Figure 3: as published, the wrong shadow was represented. The corrected Figure 3 appears below.

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Figure 3. Internal view of Hercules' courtyard (Ferretti, Indio).

There was a mistake in Table A1: as published, the included figures were too small and the source was not listed. In the corrected Table A1, the figures are no longer included. The corrected Table A1 appears below.

Table A1. Reference cases of covered courtyards after the renovation.

Reference Case	Location	Designer	Use	Typology
Santa Marta's military building	Verona, Italy	Massimo Carmassi Architects	Vertical circulation	glass layer and metal structure
British Museum	London, United Kingdom	Foster and Partners	Circulation, additional functions	glass layer and metal structure
Maritime Museum	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	Ney and Partners, Dok Arch. Rappange and Partners	New hall	glass layer and metal structure
Glasdach Staatliche Bibliothek	Passau, Germany	Awwszcz-Westner Schührer Zöhler	New library hall	glass layer and metal structure
Museum De Lakenhal	Leiden, The Netherlands	Happel Verhoeven, Julian Harrap Architects	Circulation	glass layer and metal structure
Neus Museum	Berlin, Germany	David Chipperfield Architects	Additional space, exhibition space	glass layer and metal structure
Jewish Museum	Berlin, Germany	Daniel Libeskind	Additional space, Hall	glass layer and metal structure
Museum of Hamburg History	Hamburg, Germany	Von Gerkan, Marg and Partners (gmp)	Additional space, Hall	glass layer and metal structure and cables
Maximilian Museum	Augsburg, Germany	Hochbauamt der Stadt Augsburg, Ludwig and Weiler Ingenieure	Additional space, Hall	glass layer suspended by steel cables
Beyazit State Library	Istanbul, Turkey	Tabanlıoğlu Architects	Additional space, Hall	transparent inflatable membrane structure

The authors apologize for any inconvenience caused and state that the scientific conclusions are unaffected. The original article has been updated.

Reference

1. Gaspari, J.; Fabbri, K.; Vodola, V.; Ferretti, G.; Indio, L. A Simplified Algorithm to Predict Indoor Microclimate in Case of Courtyard Covering. A Case Study for the Courtyard of Palazzo Poggi in Bologna. *Eng* **2020**, *1*, 222–239. [[CrossRef](#)]